

IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING ONLINE ADVERTISING SYSTEM AND MARKETING ENVIRONMENT IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7138879>

Advertising is not a luxury, but an urgent need for a budding entrepreneur. This will allow you to increase awareness in the market, gain a good reputation, attract paying customers. Ignoring this component of work will lead to a sad result.

In order for small business marketing campaigns to be successful, you need to build them taking into account the existing features, listen to the advice of experts. Under the influence of the development of digital technologies, the advertising market has undergone fundamental changes. Today, most companies have a significant impact as a result of the use of incentives and cross-promotions, built on the basis of issuing coupons for payment, and not from the traditional channels of the classic model, such as television, advertising, radio, outdoor advertising.

The large-scale development of the World Wide Web dates back to the last decade of the last century, when Internet pages began to appear one after another. However, advertising on these sites has long been in its infancy. Only in recent years has this situation changed dramatically

There are several reasons for this: With the development of mobile technologies and the increase in the bandwidth of existing communication channels, the number of users of the global Internet network is increasing day by day. The amount of time people spend online is also increasing. Internet use has become an hourly and even daily necessity

. Trade through Internet platforms develops the economic activity of small businesses. Currently, many businesses are using online advertising to increase their income. Online advertising is showing its results in a short period of time. Advertising, which is an integral part of marketing, also has the ability to increase the profitability of enterprises by 10% to 50%.

Internet marketing is the part of business marketing carried out using the Internet. It allows you to achieve success in business and increase your income.

Advantages:

1. Broad range of clients

Internet marketing has no limits. You can sell your product or service to any corner of the world without even opening a sales outlet.

2. Quick result

Internet marketing gives results very quickly. You can analyze every move.

3. Savings

Internet marketing is relatively low cost while delivering great results. For example, if you open an online store, you can invest less in it than in an offline store.

4. Studying the wishes of customers

You observe and analyze people's purchases, what products or services they are interested in, and their wishes in this regard. As a result, it will be possible to formulate an offer accordingly.

5. Contact with customers

You can communicate with customers in real time. As a result, their trust in you will increase. You can strengthen your relationship with them by sending emails about offers, new products and services.

6. Convenient for people

Customers will contact you at any time without worrying about working hours, as a result, your service or product can find its buyer even while you sleep. On the other hand, the customer prefers to order the product directly without spending his valuable time going to the store. Internet marketing is convenient for customers and buyers alike. Internet marketing primarily gives the consumer the opportunity to get information about products.

Any potential consumer can use the Internet to get information about the product, as well as purchase it. Although, if there is no information about one product or he cannot find it, he will probably buy another product from a competitor. The use of Internet marketing methods is aimed at saving money (on the salary of sales department employees and advertising), as well as on the expansion of the company's activities (transition from the local market to the national and international market). At the same time, both large and small companies have balanced opportunities in the fight for the market.

Unlike traditional advertising media (print, radio and television), Internet marketing is not very expensive. An important point is that, unlike traditional marketing methods of promotion, Internet marketing provides a clear statistical view of the marketing company's effectiveness. Compared to other types of media marketing (print, radio and television), Internet marketing is growing very quickly. It is becoming more and more popular not only among businesses, but also among ordinary users who want to promote their effective websites or blogs and earn money from it. However, in developed countries, Internet marketing and advertising costs account for about 5% of total advertising costs.

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